

RESEARCH ARTICLE

HR Managers' Competencies in Implementing Strategic HRM: A Causal Attribution Theory Perspective

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Abstract

Objective: Although research on Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) has surged in the last 10 years, however, the effect of HR managers' HR Competencies on SHRM implementation it's still less explored. **Methods:** This study, intends to investigate how HR managers' HR abilities contribute to the implementation of SHRM in organizations in oil & gas sector in India. The survey collects the opinions of 157 executives with more than ten years of experience on the use of SHRM and the global HR skills of HR managers in the Indian oil and gas sector. Analysis for data was conducted through Structural equation modelling. **Findings :** Findings reveal that Strategic positioner and innovator and integrator competencies are significantly related to SHRM implementation. Conversely, capability builder, change agent, credible activist, and Technology proponent competencies do not find support in implementing SHRM in this study. This study is anchored on the Causal Attribution theory. This study makes a significant contribution by empirically examining the link between the competencies of HR managers and SHRM. It also has practical implications for HRM practitioners and senior management on how to appropriately choose, prepare, and equip HR managers to enable effective implementation of SHRM. **Novelty:** This study is the first empirical study to identify the effect of HR managers' HR competencies on implementation of Strategic HRM in public sector context.

Keywords: Strategic HRM; HR Competencies; Causal attribution theory

1 Introduction

Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) is an important academic field in business management, and HR scholars have been increasingly interested in the quest for SHRM implementation. Indeed, research has transitioned from emphasizing the 'content' or design of HR systems to understand the 'process' of implementation of HR systems in organisations. HRM research and theory have primarily evolved with an emphasis on policy initiatives, processes, and systems, as well as their execution and effectiveness, with less emphasis on the managers responsible of developing,

incorporating, enforcing, and implementing HRM strategy and practice.

The multi-layered nature of SHRM is recognized from a 'process' perspective as the HR policies and practises are developed at the corporate level (intended HR practises), which may differ from those implemented in the business (actual HR practises), which may differ from those executives perceive as HR practises (perceived HR practises). As a result, if we want to understand the implementation of SHRM, we need to go beyond its content. SHRM implementation is considered an iterative process involving the design of SHRM systems, and transforming the intended practices into actual practices. By translating intended HR practises into actual HR practises, HR managers play a critical role in putting SHRM into practice. The HR managers' abilities to minimize the difference between actual and intended HR practises by minimizing the 'gap of implementation' through frequent and effective communication with executives and the 'gap of interpretation' between perceived and implemented HR practises by framing executives' perception by providing support that executives expect from the HR function⁽¹⁾. HRM researchers and practitioners accept that inadequate implementation of high-quality HRM practices may lead to unsuccessful SHRM in an organization, or effective implementation by HR managers may resurrect ineffective HR practices. The HR manager competencies also demonstrate, how they develop and implement specific HR systems, and how they create psychological agreements with employees to increase their commitment to the organizational performance⁽²⁾. Therefore, if we want to make sure that HR policies produce the desired organisational outcomes, we must understand how managers implement HR policies and the impact of the support offered by the HR department⁽³⁾.

Despite the growing importance of implementation of SHRM, the implementation literature in SHRM field is still in the infant stage and evolving. For instance, some people refer to it as a process, while others call it a result⁽⁴⁾; some authors emphasize the line managers as SHRM implementers⁽⁵⁾, while others recognize a range of organizational actors for SHRM implementation⁽⁶⁾. Furthermore, while the literature is available on organizational performance through effective SHRM implementation, there is still insufficient empirical evidence about the competence profile that HRM managers must possess to implement SHRM. This study fills knowledge gaps about the process of SHRM implementation that have been mentioned by researchers like Steffensen et al. (2019)⁽⁷⁾. Furthermore, recent assessment of the devolution research suggests that there hasn't been much discussion of the causes of HR managers' varied behaviors for implementation practises⁽³⁾. The lack of research on how the present competencies of HR professionals affect SHRM implementation is one of the gaps that this study fills.

As a result, this paper aims to empirically test HR managers' HR competencies for the effective implementation of SHRM. This study chose to seek employee perceptions of HR managers' competencies, which was developed to address concerns about HR managers' competencies to implement SHRM.

Internal stakeholders or senior management can assess these competencies through empirical investigation⁽⁸⁾. Hence, this study uses executives' perceptions of working in the oil & gas sector in India. Furthermore, the research emphasizes the varying effects of different HR competencies on SHRM implementation.

Over the past decades, SHRM has become well-known in the field of human resources. Despite its prominence in the area of strategic HRM, there is a dearth of such research when it comes to businesses from the BRICS countries⁽⁹⁾.

The oil & gas sector in India was chosen as the study's setting because of the historical growth and present development potential of SHRM in this sector. The Indian oil & gas sector has experienced several crises. Price volatility, geopolitical variables, regulatory changes, environmental concerns, and logistics challenges have all kept the sector on edge. The sector is also witnessing challenges in technological upskilling of the workforce, digital transformations, shrinking talent pool, recruiting and retaining talent pool, low sector attractiveness, aging workforce, diversity and inclusion, and rapid expansion of green technologies. Furthermore, during the last decade, studies have identified a lack of HR Professional competencies as a hindrance to the development of effective HRM in India and, in particular, Indian oil & gas sector⁽¹⁰⁾.

In order to address HR managers' competencies in the HRM implementation process, this research employed the theory of causal attributions⁽¹¹⁾. Consequently, this study will attempt to examine the effect of HR managers' global HR competencies on the efficient implementation of SHRM.

1.1 Literature Review

1.2 HR Competency

Human resource managers are expected to be valuable team members with the rest of the organizational members and contribute to the organization's success as business partners. In order for organisational resources to contribute more significantly to business objectives, the HR manager are responsible of imparting HR expertise and behavioral traits. In addition, HR managers are equipped with the competencies to collaborate with senior business leaders in strategic management and implementation.

1.3 Causal Attribution and SHRM Implementation

This research underpins the theoretical argument on attributional theory proposed by⁽¹¹⁾. Weiner addressed on how future expectations, sentiments, and performance are impacted by causal attributions. According to Weiner's application to an accomplishment context, people's emotional responses to task success or failure rely on the justifications they assign for their actions after an event occurs⁽¹¹⁾. In order to give the theory dynamism, Weiner proposed a temporal order for attributions, in which people assess the causes of behavior or actions after the occurrence.

HR managers, in addition to line managers and coworkers, can be essential in helping employees collective sense making of their work. The job of HR managers hasn't achieved much emphasis in the HRM literature. Based on this, it is stated that employees in work relationships will impact each other's ideas, feelings, and behaviors while also being influenced by the setting of their shared workplace, such as their HR manager. Hence, it is argued that through utilizing social information processing, HR managers and employees would exchange information, and as a result, a convergence of interpretations of certain work practises, i.e., causal attributions, will arise.

The line of research centered on causal attributions can be used to understand the links between HR managers' competencies and SHRM implementation. Hewett et al (2018) refer to this as the "Locus of Causality," and causal attributions evaluate employees' justifications for the significance of HR managers' Competencies. Depending on the diverse interpretations that individuals give to social stimuli, in this case HR managers competencies, employees may understand information about SHRM in various ways⁽¹²⁾.

It can be argued, drawing on the causal attribution theory, that employees will use information provided by the HR managers to comprehend organisational aims. HR managers play a critical role in helping employees appreciate why certain HR practises are implemented in the organisation by giving them information. HR managers do more than only implement HR practises. The way they communicate is particularly effective when they convey HR intentions in a distinctive, consistent, and highly consensus-oriented manner⁽¹¹⁾ since this enables employees to consistently comprehend and react correctly to the HRM system. Thus, the HR manager is crucial in ensuring that these settings are optimal so that employees receive clear HR signals.

HR managers significantly influence the effectiveness of how HR practises are implemented⁽⁶⁾. They also inform executives and employees on HR practices as part of this. Because of this, managers' explanations of the purpose behind HR practises eventually have an influence on executives' opinions of such procedure, a phenomenon known as HR attribution. Thus, HR managers attribute HR practises in their own unique ways that are likely to differ from their executives. As a result, managers' attributions of HR practises have an influence on executives' attributions. Since there may be differences between an HR manager's self-assessment and reality due to the perception attributed by employees, competencies are needed for HR managers to objectively evaluate themselves in the leadership role⁽¹³⁾.

The effectiveness with which HR managers implement HRM practises on the workplace is known as HRM implementation effectiveness. When HRM stakeholders perceive HR managers are not adequately putting HRM practises into practice, they may ascribe this to internal factors attributable to the HR managers, such as a lack of HR competencies on their part to do so.

Oil & gas sector is a service sectors where Customer response, delivery quality, timeliness, and flexibility are all becoming increasingly important. Human resources are an important role in determining delivery costs and efficiency, and their decisions are frequently made in front of consumers. Furthermore, engagement with line management by HR managers is justified by the fact that decisions are increasingly made in real time. HR decisions like work assignment and competencies are typically difficult to separate from other decisions. Aside from that, waiting for a decision will slow down the decision-making process. Changes in the mindset, organisational structure and development of HR Business Partner roles are the final factor for HR managers' engagement with executives from businesses as organizations strive to be more competitive through lowering costs⁽¹⁴⁾. Human resource management in the public sector frequently takes a unique approach For instance, the public sector might place a higher priority on principles like transparency and ownership and might have particular difficulties like political influence and financial limits. The adoption and execution of data-driven analytics in the public sector HR might be influenced by these different characteristics.

In the HRM literature, explanations for HR managers' HRM effective implementation are quite consistent. The effectiveness of HRM implementation has been found to be significantly impacted by the competencies of HR managers⁽¹⁵⁾.

1.4 Global HR Competencies and SHRM implementation

HR adds value to organization by enhancing performance and agility of human resources which is achieved by HR managers' skills and competencies. HR managers, by utilizing their competencies can identify strengths and implement the required behavioral adjustments if performance of employees isn't up to par. It is more important than ever for HR managers to figure out how to contribute in a world of constant change, complexity, and competition⁽⁴⁾.

The ability to do tasks with the desired degree of quality while according to organisational restrictions is referred to as competence. Competency is a mix of knowledge, abilities, and dispositions that may be used to perform tasks⁽¹⁶⁾.

Global HR competencies consists of six domains: Capability builder, HR innovator and Integrator strategic positioner, technology proponent, credible activist, change champion, and⁽¹⁷⁾. HR managers should have thorough knowledge of the business environment. They therefore know how to lead change and innovate within organization to remain competitive. They also have the capability to build capability, lead change and innovate to create strong organizations, propose Technology for enhancing effectiveness of the organization. The current study suggests that professional HR managers' knowledge and abilities promote efficient SHRM implementation in the firm.

1.4.1 Strategic Positioner

This competency demonstrates that HR managers have a thorough understanding of external company trends and can translate them into internal choices and actions. The function of a strategic positioner includes participation in the creation of sustainable strategies and the execution of strategic choices.

Thus, first hypothesis proposed by this study is,

H1: Strategic Positioner competency of HR manager impacts effective implementation of SHRM in Indian Oil & Gas Sector.

1.4.2 Credible Activist

This competency improved the function of HR managers by fostering self-awareness and a commitment to developing their professionalism. Through the HR system, they must be able to influence every executive, guarantee their ongoing support, and instill a sense of ownership in them. Hence the second hypothesis is

H2: Credible Activist competency of HR manager impacts effective implementation of SHRM in Indian Oil & Gas Sector.

1.4.3 Capability Builder

By fostering key organisational competencies, an effective HR manager converts the leaders' abilities into an effective and powerful organisation. Thus, the third hypothesis is,

H3: Capability builder competency of HR manager impacts effective implementation of SHRM in Indian Oil & Gas Sector.

1.4.4 Change Agent

Through the inception and maintenance of change processes, HR managers make sure that organisational activities are integrated and sustained. Hence, the fourth hypothesis is,

H4: Change Agent competency of HR manager impacts effective implementation of SHRM in Indian Oil & Gas Sector.

1.4.5 Innovative and Integrator

Innovative HR managers combine HR practices with other solutions to address business problem. They must be knowledgeable with the most recent developments in a range of HR activities, including hiring, talent management, performance management, reviews, incentives, and organisational growth. HR-related choices are frequently reliant on managers' gut instincts, past experiences, and intuition due to the qualitative nature of human management. In order to implement SHRM, HR managers' analytical role is increasingly important as the corporate environment grows more competitive and complex⁽¹⁸⁾. Hence, the fifth hypothesis is,

H5: Innovative and Integrator competency of HR manager impacts effective implementation of SHRM in Indian Oil & Gas Sector.

1.4.6 Technology Proponent

HR managers who appreciate technology may enhance interpersonal ties within the organization and enhance the organisation's external image. Hence sixth hypothesis is,

H6: Technology Proponent competency of HR manager impacts effective implementation of SHRM in Indian Oil & Gas Sector.

2 Methodology

2.1 Sample and data collection

15 companies were selected from The Economic Times' most recent ranking of the top 500 Indian organizations to test the hypotheses (ET500 2021 Ranking). The criteria used to shortlist these organizations include total revenue in FY 2021–2022, as well as market capitalization of over INR 100 crores.

The top 15 oil and gas organizations were chosen for this study from this list of 500 organizations based on their ranking. This method of selection gave us some control over the research. All of the organizations that were examined came from the same industry, were essentially the same size, employed comparable technologies, and engaged in comparable market competition. The respondents were chosen through random sampling. The questionnaire on HR Competencies and SHRM were sent to 360 executives through google form, which is fast and effective method of response collection in research⁽¹⁹⁾. A total of 157 complete responses were obtained (response rate 43.6%). Also, respondents were informed about the research and were provided with set of instructions to reduce common method bias⁽²⁰⁾.

2.2 Measure

2.2.1 Global HR Competency

The six Global HR competencies were measured by Global HR competency scale developed by Ulrich et al., (2012). The strategic positioner was measured by 3 items, credible activist by 4 items, capability builder by 3 items, change champions by 2 items, innovator, and integrator by 5 items and technology proponent by 3 items. On a five-point Likert-type scale, from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), the Executives were asked to rate the HR competency of HR managers. A sample item was "HR managers are improving utility of HR operations".

2.2.2 SHRM

SHRM was measured using the 9-item Gurbuz and Mert (2011) scale. On a scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), executives were asked to rate the presence of HR systems in their organisations. A sample item was "HR strategies are effectively integrated with your organization's strategy".

Table 1. Scale Reliability

Scales	No. of items	Cronbach alpha	Mean	Std. Dev
Strategic positioner	3	0.804	12.04	2.004
Credible activist	4	0.866	15.97	2.486
Capability builder	3	0.856	11.24	2.956
Change Champion	2	0.755	7.35	2.544
Innovative & integrator	5	0.749	21.09	3.509
Technology proponent	3	0.801	9.68	2.048
SHRM	9	0.946	25.63	9.275

A variety of preliminary analyses were carried out first. We looked for missing data and looked for univariate and multivariate outliers. The kurtosis and skewness of the distribution for each item were used to confirm its normality. Pearson correlations were used to check for potential collinearity.

3 Results and Discussion

Responses were collected and analysed with the help of SPSS version 28.0.0. Confirmatory factor analysis and path analysis was conducted through AMOS software.

Table 2 describes the sample constituting of 157 respondents. Majority of the respondents were males (66 percent). The average age and average experience of the respondents was 37.59 (SD 4.355) years and 14.92 (SD 3.106) years respectively.

Table 2. Demographic data

Variable	N=157	Percentage
Gender		
Male	104	66
Female	53	34
Experience in Years		
10 to 15	48	31
16 to 20	60	38
21 to 25	45	29
> 25	4	3
Age in Years		
31 to 40	52	33
41 to 50	77	49
51 to 55	28	18

3.1 Exploratory factor analysis

With the help of principal component analysis and varimax rotation, an exploratory factor analysis was conducted. The minimal factor loading that was requisite was set at .50. To make sure there are sufficient levels of explanation, the communalities of the scale—which show how much variation there is in each dimension—were also examined. The findings indicate that all communalities are greater than .50.

The results’ significance, $\chi^2 (354) = 544.501 (p=.000)$, suggest factor analysis as a suitable methodology. The data were suitable for factor analysis according to the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin sampling adequacy measure (MSA), which was .751. In this respect, performing a factor analysis on data with an MSA value greater than .700 is acceptable⁽²⁰⁾. This suggests that the data collected for this research showed good partial correlation. The outcome of the Bartlett’s test for sphericity is 0.0001, which is considered highly significant⁽²¹⁾. The scale’s factors were ultimately determined by the analysis’s factor solution to be 7, which accounted for 70.83 percent of the variation in the data.

Table 3. Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SP1					.843		
SP2					.835		
SP3					.830		
CredAct1		.937					
CerdAct2		.869					
CredAct3		.704					
CredAct4		.882					
CapBuild1				.827			
CapBuild2				.867			
CapBuild3				.922			
ChngCh1							.870
ChngCh2							.883
InnoInt1			.722				
InnoInt2			.780				
InnoInt3			.552				
InnoInt4			.624				
InnoInt5			.819				
TechPro1						.824	
TechPro2						.795	
TechPro3						.903	
SHRM1	.780						
SHRM2	.820						

Continued on next page

Table 3 continued

SHRM3	.908
SHRM4	.861
SHRM5	.883
SHRM6	.888
SHRM7	.711
SHRM8	.840
SHRM9	.831

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

^a Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

3.2 Model for measurement

A confirmatory factor analysis was used to assess the measurement validity (CFA). The results showed that the measurement model's structures had good convergent, discriminant, and reliability validity.

Fig 1. Measurement Model- SHRM: Strategic Human Resource Management, CredAct: Credible activist, Inno&Int: Innovative and integrator, CapBuild: Capability builder, StratPos: Strategic positioner, TechPro: Technology proponent, ChngCh: Change champion

3.3 The measurement model's findings

3.3.1 Common method bias

Table 4 demonstrates that the model proposed in this study is an over-identified model with positive freedom degrees (354). It was derived from the AMOS output. There are 81 distinct parameters in this model that need to be approximately estimated, and 435 various sample moments can be used to calculate the default model's estimates, having left 354 positive degrees of freedom (df > 0). Therefore, the model is over identified.

The assessment for common latent variables was run. Then, the results of comparing the standardised regression weights of all items for the two models showed that there were no appreciable differences between the regression weights (standardized) of items ($\Delta < .2$). Consequently, there was no common method variance with these data⁽²²⁾.

3.3.2 Results of measurement model

According to Byrne (2016), a one-factor model should always be tested in a confirmatory factor analysis before a multiple-factor framework in order of dimensionality assessment. As a result, Model 1, a single-factor model, and Model 2, a 7-factor model derived from the EFA, were both investigated and analysed in this study.

Table 4. Findings from fit statistics when using confirmatory factor analysis

Measurement model	df	χ^2	χ^2/df	CFI	GFI	RMSEA
Single factor model	375	1772.815	4.728	.468	.564	.155
7- factors model	354	544.501	1.538	.928	.824	.059

χ^2 : value of Chi-square; df: degrees of freedom; GFI: index of goodness of fit; RMSEA: root mean square error of approximation; CFI: index of comparative fit.

The model fit increases when a model has 7- factors as opposed to one, as shown in Table 4. The satisfactory ranges, as per Kline (2011), are χ^2 /df between 2.0 and 3.0, CFI higher than 0.9, and RMSEA lower than 0.06. Due to the 7- factor model's specifications being $\chi^2 (354) = 544.501, p < .001, \chi^2/df = 1.538, CFI=.928,$ and $RMSEA=.059,$ the measurement model is unidimensional.

The resulted Goodness of Fit (GFI) is .824 as opposed to the suggested value of above .90. The Root Mean Square Residual (RMR) and RMSEA, however, are both below the suggested upper limits of .05 and .08, respectively. This might suggest that the relationship is correctly predicted by the model. Even though that they do not exceed .90, the values for GFI and AGFI were sufficient because the value is allowable if above .8⁽²³⁾.

The 7-factor model thus exhibits a level that is acceptable fit in confirmatory factor analysis, indicating that the hypothesised model is adequately aligned to the observed data.

Overall, it was discovered that model 2, a 7-factor model, outperformed model 1 (a one-factor model), for all measures. The chi-square difference being statistically significant ($\chi^2_{(21)} = 1228.314, p < .001$) adds credence to the idea that Model 2 is superior to Model 1.

3.3.3 Reliability and validity measurement

After establishing the satisfactory fit of the model fit, the next step, which involved a thorough assessment of the SEM model, was carried out. CFA was performed on each of the 7 constructs- SHRM, Credible activist, innovative & integrator, capability builder, strategic positioner, technology proponent and change champion.

The loadings, which varied from .4 to .9, were all found to be significant. The composite reliability scores were between .75 and .9, and the average extracted variance vary from .40 to .684 (as shown in Table 5). The following criteria are met by these data, according to⁽²⁰⁾ and⁽²²⁾: composite reliability and factor loading were both above .5. The AVE for innovator and integrator was slightly below .5, but the composite reliability was more than .6, hence accepted. The multiple correlation coefficient square was higher than .5. All other constructs met the criteria, so each of the 7 constructs in the model demonstrated of convergent validity.

Table 5. Results for validity

Construct	Indicator	Factor Loading	Reliability (α)	CR	AVE
SHRM	SHRM1	0.731	0.946	0.947	0.667
	SHRM2	0.784			
	SHRM3	0.911			
	SHRM4	0.837			
	SHRM5	0.865			
	SHRM6	0.896			
	SHRM7	0.653			
	SHRM8	0.793			
	SHRM9	0.845			
CredAct1	CredAct1	0.928	0.866	0.871	0.634

Credible Activist

Continued on next page

Table 5 continued

	CerdAct2	0.837			
	CredAct3	0.586			
	CredAct4	0.794			
Innovative & integrating	InnoInt1	0.613	0.749	0.758	0.400
	InnoInt2	0.753			
	InnoInt3	0.410			
	InnoInt4	0.502			
	InnoInt5	0.791			
Capability Builder	CapBuild1	0.722	0.856	0.865	0.684
	CapBuild2	0.788			
	CapBuild3	0.955			
Strategic Positioner	SP1	0.791	0.804	0.807	0.584
	SP2	0.812			
	SP3	0.683			
Technology Proponent	TechPro1	0.679	0.801	0.814	0.600
	TechPro2	0.667			
	TechPro3	0.946			
Change Champion	ChngCh1	0.864	0.755	0.764	0.621
	ChngCh2	0.704			

Note: AVE: Average variance extracted; CR: Composite reliability

Table 6. Results for discriminant validity

	SHRM	Credible Activist	Innovative & integrating	Capability Builder	Strategic Positioner	Technology Proponent	Change Champion
SHRM	0.667						
Credible Activist	0.001	0.634					
Innovative & integrating	0.014	0.000207	0.400				
Capability Builder	0.002	0.000003	0.01904	0.684			
Strategic Positioner	0.022	0.000493	0.00203	0.001296	0.584		
Technology Proponent	0.002	0.000004	0.00053	0.003481	0.002916	0.600	
Change Champion	0.005	0.000024	0.00689	0.019881	0.064009	0.002116	0.621

3.3.4 Structural Model and path analysis

Figure 2 below shows the outcomes of the path analysis using the standardised regression coefficients for effect of HR global competencies on implementation of SHRM. With chi-square = 621.508 (df= 356, p =.0), RMSEA = 0.06 GFI = .803, and CFI = 0.899, this model fit the data well.

It is completely obvious from the structural model above that Hypothesis 1, strategic positioner is associated with SHRM ($\beta=0.289, p < .05$). Similarly, hypothesis 5, innovative and integrator is found positively associated with SHRM ($\beta=0.221, p < .05$).

The results of hypotheses H2, H3, H4 and H6 were rejected as the results were not found significant.

Understanding the impact of HR managers' HR Competencies on implementing SHRM in the business is the purpose of this study. To achieve this objective, this study investigated the impact of six Global HR competencies namely Change Champion, Strategic Positioner, Capability Builder Credible activist, Technology Proponent, Innovative & Integrator on SHRM. This study contributes to the body of knowledge regarding the Global HR competencies of HR professionals, which is currently in its infancy, by focusing on the impact of Global HR competencies on the implementation of SHRM based on causal attribution through employees.

Fig 2. Path analysis

Table 7. Results of path analysis

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p	Result
H1: Strategic Positioner –> SHRM	0.289	0.157	1.974	**	Supported
H2: Credible Activist –> SHRM	-0.023	0.126	-0.184	0.854	Not supported
H3: Capability Builder –> SHRM	-0.063	0.103	-0.609	0.543	Not supported
H4: Change champion –> SHRM	-0.113	0.084	-1.342	0.180	Not supported
H5: Innovative & integrator –> SHRM	0.221	0.165	1.969	**	Supported
H6: Technology proponent –> SHRM	-0.06	0.145	-0.416	0.678	Not supported

SE= Standard error, CR=Critical Ratio, ** p< 0.05, $\chi^2=621.508$, df=356, $\chi^2/df= 1.746$, CFI=.899, GFI=.803, RMSEA=.06

The significant positive relationship between Strategic Positioner and SHRM ($\beta =0.289$, $p<.05$) is the result of HR initiatives in those companies where they cocreated their organizations’ strategic responses to business conditions. Almost all organizations have included green product mix in their business lines like Compressed Natural Gas (CNG), blending of ethanol and electric charging stations at petrol pumps and stations. Also, all of them are forming joint ventures for foraying into the business of renewable energy sources. HR has identified key positions for new business of renewable energy and commenced recruitment of experienced executives at lateral basis. Most of the sampled companies in this study are central public sector enterprise (CPSE) which recruits at entry level only. Attracting experienced managers on lateral basis is challenging due to regulatory guidelines on compensation and benefits structure, which is fixed as per salary grades and cannot be negotiated. Hence, respondents perceived this competency as strategic positioner which is critical for adoption of principles of SHRM.

Competency Innovative & Integrator was found significantly related to SHRM ($\beta =0.221$, $p<.05$). The t-value is higher than 1.96⁽²⁴⁾. These organizations have transformed the role of HR from transactional to strategic by incorporating employer value proposition in recruitment, work force segmentation and long-term recruitment plan in their staffing and workforce planning, inclusion of sustainability in KPI for performance management. One of the organizations has started the ‘Failure Award’ also to promote executives to adopt new ways of doing things. They are awarded even if they fail in the project /work but share valuable learnings to the organization on their endeavour.

Most of the companies selected in this study are Central Public Sector Undertaking, which is governed by the government guidelines. So, HR managers don't have much leeway to design the HR policy beyond the guidelines. HR professionals' competency technology proponent was not found positively related to SHRM ($\beta = -0.06$, $p = .678$), similarly the results for impact on SHRM by credible activist ($\beta = -0.023$, $p = .854$), capability builder ($\beta = -0.063$, $p = .543$), and change champion ($\beta = -0.113$, $p = .180$) were found insignificant. This can be explained by the fact that these Central Public Sector Undertakings operate primarily in accordance with SOPs. There are hierarchical systems and a bureaucratic method of operation. Decisions on various policies are to be approved by competent authority and by following approving route and this process takes some time. This competency was therefore not considered significant in this study.

3.4 Theoretical Implication

The results of this study are significant for several reasons. This study makes an important contribution by empirically examining the connection between SHRM implementation and HR managers' HR Competencies. By using the causal attribution theory⁽¹¹⁾ to the situation of employees' attributions for effective HRM in implementing SHRM practises in their organisation, the research was able to identify internal antecedents of SHRM implementation, i.e., HR competences. Executives' attributions are brought into our empirical work, which builds on earlier HRM literature's findings regarding HRM implementation efficacy⁽⁶⁾.

SHRM researchers have recently turned more significantly on attribution theory to explain perceptions of executives towards intended HR practices designed by organization⁽¹²⁾, and HRM publications are increasingly concentrating on attribution theory's application to HRM. As a response to more empirical research on the topic, this study examined the effectiveness of HRM implementation and the role of HR managers competences in it, using the causal attribution theory.

3.5 Managerial Contribution

The major managerial implication from the results of this study is to help HR managers identify competencies and skills between HRM and effective implementation of SHRM where overlap and synergies between the two areas are possible. This paper offers senior managers and HRM practitioners' insight on how to choose, train, and equip HR managers for successful SHRM implementation. To reflect on their own HRM implementation behaviours, HR managers can use the attributions that influence HRM implementation effectiveness. Employee attributions may help HR managers choose which attributions to invest in by helping them consider whether internal or external factors are to blame for the efficacy of HRM implementation. This allows HR managers to actively seek assistance within the organization. This study strengthens the need for managers to get training on how to frame conversations about HR practises in a way that promotes positive attitudes and ensures that messages are consistent with the practises' intended outcomes.

Top managers must comprehend how the HR practises system is seen by both HR managers who apply them and executives as end-users since intentions may not always translate as expected. In practise, this calls for a clear communication plan to make sure HR managers receive consistent signals about the objectives of policies and practices, which are then communicated to executives during implementation.

3.6 Limitation and Future research

Particularly when it comes to a construct like competency, which is likely to both affect and be influenced by the same variable such as SHRM, the cross-sectional design of this research limits the assertions about the hypothesized relationship and causal direction. Longitudinal research may be chosen in the future. Additionally, this study was carried out in India, which has a unique cultural characteristic leading to a management style distinct from western management style. Future studies may take into account the cultural perspectives. Hence, qualitative research on competencies and SHRM variables might be chosen for future studies.

4 Conclusion

The role of HR managers is found to be critical in implementation of SHRM. The objective of this study was to empirically examine how the Global HR Competencies affected the implementation of SHRM. The study made an important contribution by furthering the causal attribution perspective of HRM. This study has advanced the SHRM literature by exploring the relationship between Six Global HR Competencies as an antecedent of effective implementation of SHRM. This study concludes by supporting significant influence of competencies Strategic Positioner, and Innovative & integrator on implementing SHRM, whereas no influence of capability builder, technological proponent change champion, and credible activist on SHRM. The HR managers must develop Global HR competencies to lead change towards sustainable practices and establish a sustainable and

effective SHRM in the organization.

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